

A PSYCHOANALYTICAL STUDY OF CHINELO OKPARANTA'S *UNDER THE UDALA TREES*

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Abstract

In literature, psychoanalysis examines the conscious and unconscious minds of authors, readers and characters and interprets motives, desires, conflicts and fears through dreams, symbols and defense mechanisms to reveal meanings in the text. Existing studies on *Under the Udala Trees* have addressed sociological discourses such as trauma, homoerotic desire, war, self-acceptance, and homophobia. However, scant attention has been paid to the behavioural patterns and thought processes of homosexual characters in the novel, using Sigmund Freud's structural model of psychoanalytical theory. The study, therefore, explored a psychoanalytical reading of Chinelo Okparanta's *Under the Udala Trees*, focusing on the behavioural patterns and thought processes of the homosexual characters in the novel. The study adopted Freud's structural model of psychoanalytical theory because it allowed for the investigation of characters' behaviours, motives, and traits towards homosexuality. The novel, *Under the Udala Trees*, was subjected to critical and textual analysis, while references were made to secondary texts where applicable. In *Under the Udala Trees*, lesbian characters such as Ijeoma, Ndidi, and Amina are considered as fearless and narcissistic as a result of their id. Some of their homosexual acts are suppressed and repressed due to the mediation of the ego. Homosexual characters such as Ijeoma and Ndidi also remained rebellious and deviant towards the constructs of the superego. This study gives an insight into the psyche of the homosexual characters, which is in tune with the events that unfold in the novel.

Keywords: Psychoanalysis, Homosexuality, Id, Ego, Superego, Novel, Chinelo Okparanta.

Introduction

Psychoanalytic theory, propounded by Sigmund Freud, helps in understanding the construction and reconstruction of personal, collective, and sexual impulses. It recognizes the function of developing controls over uninhibited motives of several fantasies, uncovers hidden thoughts and feelings that influence an individual's

behaviour, and traces the dynamics of personality development that is related to the practice of psychoanalysis. In psychoanalysis, the human mind is divided into two distinct systems, namely the conscious and the unconscious. According to Freud, the id belongs to the unconscious, which is governed by the pleasure principle. It is a reservoir of instincts, wishes, and needs. The id is an entirely unconscious, dark, and inaccessible part of the personality. It is made up of its personal needs and desires. The ego deals with reality and is responsible for organizing behaviour and experience. It works by reason and considers the rules, norms, and etiquette that influence one's behaviour. The superego is the ethical component of the personality and provides the moral standards by which the ego operates. Lapsley and Stey opine that the superego is "an agency that seeks to enforce the striving for perception, as it holds out the ego ideal standards and moralistic goals" (6). They see the superego as a precipitate of family life and the conscience of one's personality. Jacques Lacan is also another important proponent of psychoanalytical theory. He is famous for psychoanalytical models such as the mirror stage and the orders of the mind. Other proponents of psychoanalytic theory include Anna Freud, Adler, Erikson, and Carl Jung.

In African literature, there have been different projections about the inclusion of homosexual characters in different African literary works. The inclusion of these gay and lesbian characters has been portrayed in a positive and negative light. Some writers see it as un-African and as a taboo in public discourse, while the other faction seeks support and tolerance towards homosexuals by projecting their characters in a positive light. Chris Dunton explored the monothematic and stereotypical portrayal of homosexuality in novels such as *Our Sister Killjoy*, *The Interpreters*, *A Few Nights and Days*, and *No Past, No Present, No Future*. Kole Omotosho's *The Edifice* is a product of the protagonist's entanglement with Westernization. In Wole Soyinka's *The Interpreters*, Sagoe's preference for homosexuality is a result of colonialism. Contemporary African writers such as Chinelo Okparanta, Jude Dibia, Frank Edozien, Trifonia Obono, and Freida Ekotto have projected their characters in a positive light in their works to advocate for tolerance and support towards non-normative sexualities.

This study, therefore, attempts to explore the behavioural patterns and thought processes of homosexual characters in Chinelo Okparanta's *Under the Udala Trees*, using Sigmund Freud's structural model of psychoanalytical theory as a lens to analyse the formation of their sexual identity and desires.

The Id As An Unconscious Component of Homosexual Characters in *Under the Udala Trees*

Neil Carlson defines the id as the "unconscious source of bodily needs, impulses, and desires, especially those related to aggression and the sexual drive" (453). From

Carlson's position, the id stems from the unconscious and acts in accordance with the pleasure principle. The pleasure principle, in this context, is a force that deals with the immediate gratification of impulses and desires. In *Under the Udala Trees*, Ijeoma succumbs to her id because same-sex desires have been the source of her bodily needs. She is always attracted to the same gender because of the development of her emotional impulses and desires. This attraction is evident when she meets other homosexual characters like her. As she sees Amina, she describes her affection for her and expresses homoerotic desire towards her. This action validates Sigmund Freud's definition of the id:

It is filled with energy reaching it from the instincts, but it has no organization, produces no collective will, but only striving to bring about the satisfaction of the instinctual needs subject to the observance of the pleasure principle (105).

By tagging her beauty as irresistible, she could not control her id as she bows to it. Through their preference for same-sex actions, both characters enable their id to overwhelm them as they both express same-sex pleasure. Ijeoma narrates:

Back in the hovel, our towels fell to the floor. In the near darkness, our hands moved across our bodies. We took in with our fingers the curves of our flesh, the grooves. Our hands, rather than our voices, seemed to do the speaking. Our breaths mingled with the night sounds. Eventually our lips met. This was the beginning, our bodies being touched by the fire that was each other's flesh (140-141)

Her homoerotic impulses become active as she sees homosexuality as natural in her way of thinking. To her, homosexuality is not an abnormal sexuality, and by extension, her mind is focused on achieving the pleasure principle.

Another instance where she finds a natural attraction with a girl is during her meeting with the mentholatum girl who came to get things from Adaora's shop. Their mindset immediately moves to the pleasure principle of lesbianism. They both expressed desires towards themselves. Ijeoma gives an account of how the girl showed her lesbian signs:

I was wearing a navy-blue polka-dotted dress that formed a V-line at the junction between my breasts, and I saw the moment when her eyes flickered down to that area, and paused, before darting back up to meet my eyes. (209).

Whenever she sees or thinks about her preference for a same-sex relationship, her drives begin to search for immediate satisfaction, and this makes her id move on to what her orgasm needs. This is proven when she thinks about Amina. When she needs to satisfy her sexual desires, she masturbates while thinking about the sexual experiences with Ndidi. After realising this pleasure, the reduction of tension is experienced. This is an analogy of a person eating or drinking water to satisfy his/her hunger or thirst, compared to how the author has portrayed the character in her dire need to have sex with her fellow gender. She narrates:

Alone in my bedroom, I was full of thoughts of Ndidi. As I changed into my nightgown and climbed into bed, there she was, taking up all spaces, right down to cracks and crevices of my mind. I could not help myself, even with Mama in the next room over. I found myself having a physical reaction to her in my thoughts. I became so engorged, so swollen with desire, that the only relief I could think was to pleasure myself, a thing that I had hardly ever done before – Only once or twice in our secondary school in Oraifite (228).

The id is ignorant of judgements of values; that is, there is no morality at the id stage of her mindset. This can be seen in Ijeoma's second meeting with Ndidi. Ndidi takes her to a lesbian gathering where they can see themselves as free from the socio-cultural norms of the community. Ijeoma struggles with the superego as she forgets her mother's Bible studies. The id comes into play here. In her mindset, she removes anything like a moral discourse as she succumbs to Ndidi's romance. Both characters decide to forget about the realities of their present community to abide by the pleasure principle of the id.

Ijeoma is a character who always yearns for pleasurable survival. This is in relation to Freud's instinctual cathexes, which result in a great reservoir of libido. Freud describes libido as a crucial component of the id, showing the person's drives and desires for sexual activity. The mindset of several homosexual characters in the novel is presented with sexual qualities that are influenced by biological, psychological, and social factors. That is, readers are made to infer the psychological portraiture of homosexual characters, which is depicted by internal personality, while the social construction of these characters is characterized by the influences of peer groups, work, and family. By psychoanalysing the structure and formation of these characters, sexual desires are pivotal to the explication of the novel. This is evident as Ndidi tries to create this life instinct with Ijeoma to achieve pleasurable survival in a heterosexual-dominated society. When Ijeoma visits her house, she moves close to her and seduces her to make love to her. Ijeoma narrates:

She took my hand in hers and brought it to her waistline. In one swift motion, she unzipped her skirt at the side zipper. The skirt loosened, and she brought my hand inside. (234).

This action further aligns with the id of the two homosexual characters in the novel. Both Ijeoma and Ndidi have to follow their libido, which comes naturally from their minds. Their minds towards homosexuality are what Freud qualifies as “id-ridden” because they both have natural impulses that require an urgent need for satisfaction. Through this, the creation of these characters has helped to showcase how libido influences the sexual desires of homosexuals in the novel.

At a point, Ijeoma’s id takes total control of her as she denounces heterosexuality. This shows that she is no longer ashamed of her sexuality. She tells Chibundu this after he discovered a series of love letters that were written to Ndidi. This is evident as the mind of Ijeoma shows a pleasure-seeking mechanism that has overshadowed her. All she desires is gratification, irrespective of the criticisms that follow her. She dismisses the aberration of homosexuality that heterosexuals have propounded.

It is well known that the id structure of homosexual characters precedes the ego. This process begins from their childhood stage, which later metamorphoses into a well-structured ego. The id, according to Freud,

contains everything that is inherited, that is present at birth, is laid down in the constitution- above all, therefore, the instincts, which originate from the somatic organization, and which find a first psychical expression here (in the id) in forms unknown to us (107).

While Ijeoma’s mindset of searching for pleasure shows up, her ego tends to fight her id by emphasizing the realities of society. She suppresses her id, but she is often surprised at how Ndidi remains undaunted in carrying her sexuality in a normal manner. Ijeoma tries to reduce the tension between herself and her mother by succumbing to her mother's wishes to be accepted into society. She later got married to Chibundu, a heterosexual character, but her id still goes back to the mental image of the desired object (Ndidi) as a way of satisfying her needs. In one of her letters, she confesses to her that “he is my husband, yes, but you are the one that I love”. (324). Her id expresses her mental image to Ndidi as the object of pleasure. Ijeoma pushes her id back to her subconscious and hides under the cloak of normalcy so that she can blend in and raise eyebrows in society.

She rejects the sexual desires of Chibundu in favour of Ndidi. She explains to Ndidi how she feels about Chibundu. She writes:

... I can't wait for my baby to be here. I love the precious little thing already and can't wait to hold him or her in my arms. Poor Chibundu. I do not care for him. But not a moment passes when I don't wish you were the one here with me, the one with whom I would raise my child. (325).

Anytime she expresses her delight in same-sex relationships, her id is unaware of the societal norms and realities. She tends to satisfy her desires above all ideological stances on heterosexuality. Ijeoma gives an account of how she took Amina to her hovel, where they clearly expressed their sexuality with freedom. The expression of homosexuality in the hovel is significant because it gives an account of what goes on in their closet, without the fear of being caught by the grammar school teacher.

Ndidi is presented as a more developed homosexual who is not ashamed of her sexuality. This is seen in her actions and thoughts towards same-sex relationships. Her id takes absolute control of her. She feels no remorse towards her sexual identity, as she also attempts to lure potential lesbians into the homosexual circle. That is why she takes Ijeoma to the lesbian get-together. Ndidi allows her id to take charge as she disregards all contrary views about homosexuality. She passionately dances and kisses Ijeoma and expresses her optimism towards the acceptance of homosexuality in the near future. Rather than forfeit her desire to search for homosexual characters, she proceeds to get pleasure at every point. She replies to Ijeoma's letters without the fear of Ijeoma's husband knowing about it. Her overt sexual advances eventually allowed Ijeoma to finally succumb to her id by divorcing Chibundu. In contrast to Ndidi's id taking absolute control of her mind, Amina later suppressed her id to conform to the society's ego, which abides by norms and values. This shows that the suppression of Amina's id results from the events and affiliations that move into her consciousness. Some minor homosexual characters in the novel also keep their id in control as they also practise it secretly.

The id governs Amina's personality. She is presented with a specific behaviour that attempts to accomplish her daily needs irrespective of the drawbacks. In her case, she lives on the street until Ijeoma sees her and helps her by taking her to her guardian's house for shelter.

The Ego as a Mediator in the Minds of Homosexual Characters in *Under the Udala Trees*

The ego acts as a regulating mechanism that enables the person to resist several gratifying needs to conform to the functioning of the external world. Carducci asserts that "the ego meets the needs and desires of the id by operating on the reality principle. From his position, the mindset of an individual needs to align with the

rules and norms regardless of the irrational needs of the id. In the novel, Amina had to resist the gratifying needs of her id by betraying her lesbian lover, Ijeoma, and marrying an Hausa man. The ability to quit homosexuality for heterosexuality brings out the reality principle of what happens in her environment. Her ego allows her to banish the thoughts of homosexuality, followed by the slow development from her “pleasure ego” into a “reality ego”. Her ability to be coerced into heterosexuality is further compared with a rational and emotional mind. These two comparisons imply that she was made to choose between society’s ideological thoughts over her same-sex feelings. Freud, in *Introductory Lectures on Psychoanalysis*, argues that:

An ego seeks to obtain pleasure which is assured through taking account of reality, even though it is pleasure postponed or diminished (402-403).

The ego manifests when she disobeys the id by breaking the news of her marriage to the grammar school teacher and Adaora. This makes Ijeoma feel sad as she expresses Amina’s betrayal for dumping her. Ijeoma says:

Amina cleared her throat. She looked at me as she spoke. It was a simple declaration: “There is a Hausa boy who wants to marry me”. It was not at all characteristic of me, but in that moment, I burst out with one quick *ha*, the vocalization of shock. (199).

Ijeoma feels betrayed by Amina’s decision to switch from homosexuality to heterosexuality. She expresses her disappointment. This further shows that the ego mediates with the id, which brought about Amina’s modification of her sexuality, which occurs due to the influence of the grammar school teacher in convincing her.

After Amina’s engagement, Ijeoma deliberates on whether she should conform to heterosexuality or remain homosexual. Her mind struggles to strike a balance between her primitive drives and the moralistic values of the society. She gets confused about the legality of homosexuality as she seeks a solution to satisfy her id, and at the same time, the demands of society. Ijeoma tries to suit her desires and her mother’s ideology. Her biased favour of homosexuality over her mother’s religious inclinations creates discontent in the two other personality structures. This is so because it is believed that the ego tends to be more loyal to the id. Ijeoma prefers to express her love to Ndidi over Chibundu because she believes that she is more comfortable with homosexuality and, at the same time, pretends to stay in a heterosexual marriage with Chibundu. This decision further paves the way for the superego to punish Ijeoma’s moves with feelings of guilt, inferiority, and anxiety.

Ijeoma suffers from guilt feelings after every sexual intercourse that she has with Ndidi. She always remembers her mother's Bible lessons whenever she engages in intimacy with Ndidi. Ijeoma expresses her guilt as a result of not loving Chibundu. She expresses her disappointment in the letter that she wrote to Ndidi. Another case of guilt is when the grammar school teacher discovered that she and Amina were having a homosexual affair. His reference to the Bible and the Koran, represented by the superego, incurs guilt as their conscience begins to prick them. Both characters begin to harbour the negative feelings that had built up tension in their minds, which affected them psychologically.

Ndidi is portrayed as a different character whose ego is subdued because she is not concerned with societal values. She does not allow anybody to convince her and scouts for lovers. Ndidi keeps in touch with several lesbians, as she is also responsible for introducing Ijeoma into the lesbian circle. This indicates that she privileges the pleasure principle over the reality principle. To Ndidi, homosexuality is natural, and she remains adamant about her decision.

As Ijeoma faces a dilemma about her sexual orientation, she is guided by her ego in her decision-making as her ego struggles to find a way around the id. This situation aligns with Elizabeth and Albert Allgeier's submissions about the ego in *Sexual Interactions*. They opine that:

The ego is shaped by conscious perceptions and contacts with the external world. It seeks to satisfy the demands of the id in light of the constraints of the real world. In working out a realistic strategy to satisfy our needs, the ego must satisfy three masters. It must deal with the id, which wants the satisfaction of needs. It must take into account the demands of external reality, which prohibit many selfish behaviours. Finally, it must satisfy the last sub-system of personality to emerge superego (75).

By this, Ijeoma's ego tries to satisfy her primary needs (homosexual desires), and at the same time, it takes into account the realistic part of what happens around her regarding homosexuality. The demands of the external reality further create confusion in her sexual orientation, and she also seeks to satisfy the superego. This occurred when Ijeoma went to the church to pray about heterosexuality. She hopes to get an answer to settle the whole confusion that runs in her mind about homosexuality. This is because the moral grounds of the society perceived by her ego have transformed to become part of her personality.

The traumatic experiences resulting from Amina's betrayal bring Ijeoma back to her reality principle. Here, her ego becomes completely functional as she explores

other aspirations that contrast with her undying love for Amina. Months after Amina's betrayal, she moves back to her mother's business as she pretends to love Chibundu. This temporary development is just to conform to the demands of her ego and superego to please her mother.

To overcome guilt, anxiety, and inferiority, Ijeoma develops defence mechanisms. These mechanisms persist in the interactions of the three components. The essence of bringing in defence mechanisms is that it steps in when the ego of the characters fails. With this, the defence mechanisms of these characters replace the unpleasant feelings about them and make good things feel better for them. These mechanisms are used by the ego when the character's id is in a clash with the moral values represented by the superego. This is further shared by Ndidi, who encourages her not to panic about her lesbian identity, claiming that there are positive signs ahead for accepting their sexual orientation. She tries to rewrite and challenge several doctrines to suit her interest in homosexuality. She attempts to support the claim that homosexuality is normal. Ijeoma does this by explaining the content that is in Hebrews 8. The defence mechanisms that run through her mindset are to distort the African realities about homosexuality. These mechanisms help her defend against the anxious feelings to maintain her memories that aid in summarizing her personal same-sex experiences with Ndidi. This personal experience is what Freud generalizes into the self-schema.

Under the ego defence mechanisms, the character's personality expresses many concepts under the operation of the ego. Ijeoma also tries to modify certain painful events that arise as a result of diverse homophobic reactions of society. Her defence mechanisms come to her rescue through selective memory. While interacting with her daughter, she keeps the secret of being a lesbian for a long time. This is to enable her to forget the painful experiences resulting from forced heterosexual marriage with Chibundu. She prefers to modify specific experiences. This runs along the lane of her ego, which tends to mediate between the forces of her id and the superego.

Amina's ego moves to the denial stage, making her forget about unpleasant incidents in their homosexual relationship with Ijeoma at the grammar school teacher's house, where they succumb to their id while making love. During this process, they are caught red-handed and scolded for the act. Years after, Amina finds a boy to marry. Ijeoma challenges her for betraying her by switching over to heterosexuality. Amina's ego overwhelms her as she employs the denial factor of her defence mechanisms to banish every thought of the unpleasant incidents that happened. She expresses her disappointment in Amina's silence and betrayal of her lesbian love towards her. Her inability to pay attention to Ijeoma is to forget and deny that they once had lesbian sex. To her now, same-sex marriage is unpleasant, and she only sees silence and ignorance about old events as a way of evading the questions that Ijeoma asked her about their relationship.

At the same time, Amina's ego tries to conform to the social realities, norms, etiquette, and rules in deciding on the way to behave; that is, her ego tries to satisfy the superego. This is in contrast to Ndidi, whose id controls her mindset. It is viewed that Ndidi's id is far stronger than the ego, as she remains adamant about her sexuality. This bears out Freud, who opines that the ego is weak compared to the id, which is headstrong. According to him, the best the ego can do is to stay on, leading the id in the right direction and claiming some credit at the end of each action. The mediation between the character's mind shows how the ego mediates with their id. Amina had to settle for a Hausa man and also migrate with him. Her ego conforms to the superego because she has initially dropped all that society considers deviant.

At a point, Ijeoma's conscience takes a turn about her sexuality when she starts to get worried about her mother's bible lessons. This happened after she followed Ndidi to the lesbian community. She cares about her religious institution. This co-existence also pushes her to seek the face of God about her sexuality. She trusts God to answer her prayers concerning her sexuality as she hopes to hear from Him. With this, her inner mind begins a struggle with society. Her ego comes to mediate between the two opposing forces again. The ego tends to yield to the id as she points to the hollows of the church. Instead of continuing to pray to God to seek the legality of her sexual orientation, her ego succumbs to her id as she reminisces about the beautiful and romantic moments that she shared with Amina.

In the latter part of the novel, Amina's conscience also pricks her, stipulating that she should stop the homosexual act. This causes a rift with Ijeoma. The rift shows that the id and ego are in constant conflict with each other. This causes conflict within Amina's mind. She claims to have a dream that often triggers her to quit homosexuality. This further shows that the ego still affects the character. She claims that the dreams that have been occurring to her have made her feel some guilt. With this, the ego still affects her. The ego also tries to mediate with the superego to create a force between her primitive thoughts and the realities of society.

On Ijeoma's part, her ego makes her battle between two opposing forces (id versus superego). The opposing forces can be tagged as homophobic attitudes versus her quest for lesbian love and sex. She tries to wobble between the two concepts through her ego-driven mindset, but her happiness is insufficient. Her id comes out stronger as she struggles to tame her feelings for the same sex, most importantly, with her euphoric thoughts of Ndidi. She narrates:

Alone in my bedroom, I was full of thoughts of Ndidi. As I changed into my nightgown and climbed into bed, there she was, taking up all the spaces, right down to the cracks and crevices of my mind. I could

not help myself, even with Mama in the next room over. I found myself having a physical reaction to her in my thoughts. I became so engorged, so swollen with desire [...]

Memories of my Bible studies with Mama rushed back to me yet again, no matter how much I tried to put them away from my mind [...] but suddenly here was this panicked dream, as if to mockingly ask me how I could even presume to think happiness was a thing within my reach. (228-229).

The Superego Personality Structure of Homosexual Characters in *Under the Udala Trees*

The superego is the component of an individual's personality that acts as a moral conscience. It represents societal norms and standards and strives for perfection. Its role is to control the id, guide the ego, and promote moral behaviour. The superego also includes the individual's ego ideals, goals, and psychic agency that controls one's expression of feelings, fantasies, actions, and drives.

In *Under the Udala Trees*, the first influence of the superego on Ijeoma, as the protagonist, is her identification with her parents, who are heterosexual. As her development continues, the superego subdues her mind as she faces ideological differences between herself and Adaora. It is well known that her superego is based on the parents' superego. This occurs as a result of her identification with her parents. The superego imposes the ideas of her parents on her. This illustration follows Freud's assertion that:

[...] a child's superego is in fact constructed on the model not of its parents but its parents' superego; the contents which fill it are the same and it becomes the vehicle of tradition and of all the time-resisting judgements of value which have propagated themselves in this manner from generation to generation. (95-96).

Through this, readers can pinpoint the psychology of two forces in the discourse of homosexuality. There is a clash against Ijeoma's id. The superego objects to her sexual orientation as a result of the cultural rules of society. This enhances the anxious thoughts and feelings of the character about her sexual orientation. She is faced with a lot of hostile values, which makes her question herself. This is seen in the interaction between Adaora, who represents the heterosexual structure, and

Ijeoma, as a homosexual. She gets fearful of the superego, which is believed to be the moralistic approach to her id. She narrates:

At home that night, the panicked dreams were worse than on all the preceding nights combined. Throughout my sleep, I was confronted with Mama's scolding face, her reprimanding finger-wagging at me, threatening to poke out an eye. The images of Mama were interspersed with a thunderous sound that, in the dream, was the voice of God, scolding also like Mama, reprimanding, condemning me for my sins (235).

At a point, the mother seeks perfection for her daughter. She tries to change her behavioural patterns and traits as she creates a negative conscience, making the protagonist's mindset send a message of criticism against her sexual drives, feelings, thoughts, actions, and fantasies. Her superego comes in the form of the conscience, which nudges her to feel guilty. This guilt also arises as a result of the hostile and subjugated nature of her parents and guardians. Schwartz writes that "the superego acts as the conceptualisation of the inner critic". The inner critic points to the psychic subpersonality of Ijeoma. The inner personality of Ijeoma judges her behaviour. This sense of judgement arises from what people perceive about their sexual orientation, and in African society, it is deemed an abomination; hence, homophobic reactions begin to set in. Reading from the author's projection of Ijeoma as a character, this inner critic acts as an inner voice that attacks her actions. Through the grammar school teacher's reaction to Ijeoma and Amina's lesbian relationship, the author projects an inner motive that depicts the current situation that the characters are in. On that spot, the characters are portrayed with a sense of low self-esteem and bad feelings. In Ijeoma's mindset, one can tag her inner critic as "the guilt tripper", "the moulder", and "the inner controller".

The second part of the superego system overwhelms both Ijeoma and Ndidi. The ideal system in which the second part paves the way for portraying the characters' aspirations, decision-making is depicted through the characters' dialogues and actions. Ndidi, a more fearless and determined lesbian, sticks to the ideal system as she focuses on her career aspirations while she selects her sexuality. This is done carefully as she keeps it secret from her family and friends. This is to shield her from the moralistic stand of society. Her first system communicates to her about her sexuality as a bad precedent to the society, but the ideal system ensures that she conforms to the standards of the society in the open while she adopts her homosexual identity in secret. She only expresses her feelings when Ijeoma visits her at home or through the writing of letters. She writes a letter to Ijeoma and fantasises about the legality of homosexuality. This shows the two-functioning part

of the superego system. Her conscience keeps her in check, while the ideal system also makes her keep her sexuality secret while she pretends to conform to the standards of the society. She narrates her sad feelings in her letter as she recalls how she ran into her mother, who couldn't stop gushing over the fact that Ijeoma is pregnant (328). Ijeoma admits in the letter that she could not fight for her sexual orientation due to homosexuality, but she admits that she misses her daily.

This also happens to Ijeoma when she narrates her secret affair with Ndidi. She succumbs to the superego as she explains that the hostile nature of society makes her hide her preference for lesbianism. The author portrays her as a weak figure according to the societal standards due to the influence of the superego. She grows timidly as she says that "I felt the urge to explain that I had not tried to keep it from him, not really. Yes, I had hidden it, but also I had not hidden it" (329). With this, the author enables the reader to see through the inner personality of the character. Her id signifies her interest, but it got suppressed and crushed by the superego.

Her mother's demands oppose Ijeoma's sexual demands; hence, there is a clash between the mother's socio-cultural norms and Ijeoma's quest for same-sex marriage, which is driven by the id. Within the superego, which is represented by the moral values of the society, Ijeoma's ego finds a difficult task in reconciling the two. She finds it very difficult to please her mother, who insists on her marrying Chibundu while she yearns for lesbianism. Through the character's motive, the author portrays how homosexuals face the challenge of acceptability in African society. With the interference of the superego on her id, one can note that the character's psychology conflicts with the two other systems. Through the inner thoughts that pervade the character's mind, the superego tends to control her by presenting to her what society perceives to be right or wrong, and these create guilt feelings about her sexual orientation. The interference of the superego further points to the sense of morality and what the African society infuses into the ideologies of the character on what can be regarded as a taboo.

The forces of the superego influence Amina's decision to succumb to the guilt created by her conscience. This happened when the grammar school teacher infused some religious teaching into her to discourage her from homosexuality. Her psyche immediately succumbs to the demands of the grammar school teacher. She looks so helpless in her decision-making as she was forced to leave Ijeoma for a Hausa boy. Her ability to sacrifice her id in favour of the superego further shows the kind of character that she is. The superego is seen to influence her decision-making, which further infuriates Ijeoma, her lesbian lover. The state of helplessness resulting from the influence of authority or societal norms can be linked to repression. The repression of her id makes the superego come out as an authoritative force over her ego in the form of her conscience or an unconscious feeling of guilt. Through her internal traits and behavioural patterns, she can be regarded as

contrasting with Ndidi. The latter still maintains strong id-driven impulses, irrespective of the strong force of the superego over her.

Regarding the conflict between Chibundu and Ijeoma on her behavioural approach to sexuality, Ijeoma's conscience seems to play on her while she deceives him into loving him, whereas she is in love with Ndidi. She, therefore, sees the need to apologise to him. The actions and motives behind her apology bring out the function of where the superego comes into effect. This is one of the essences of characterising her motives to show how the mind relates between the pleasure principle and what really comes in the external world. Watts and Hook write about the duty of the superego:

The primary function of the superego is to inhibit and squash any unconscious impulse of the id. It also tries to make the ego act morally, to take moral as well as rational considerations into account when deciding how to act in a certain situation. Lastly, the superego tries to guide the person towards perfection in what he says, does and thinks. (60).

Ijeoma is portrayed to be an amphigenic invert in the novel. This shows that her inversion shows how she succumbs to her id because she refers to the sexual satisfaction from the opposite sex as unattainable or unsuitable. In this case, she sees sexual pleasure and satisfaction from Ndidi as a must. Although she gets married to Chibundu, she sees their union solely as a function of reproduction. The essence of procreation is to satisfy the desires of her mother, who also serves as the superego, but she finds pleasure with Ndidi. This is evident when she narrates to Adaora about her decision to leave his house because Chibundu is not appealing to her, hence the need for her to switch from forced heterosexuality to homosexuality.

Conclusion

The study provides a detailed psychoanalysis of homosexual characters in Okparanta's *Under the Udala Trees*. The id, ego, and superego of characters such as Ijeoma, Amina, and Ndidi are explored to examine the primal state of sexual desires, mediation, and the struggle against the norms of the society.

In the novel, homosexual characters such as Ndidi and Ijeoma succumb to their id and align with their same-sex desires, irrespective of the dictatorial tendencies of the superego. In contrast, Amina suppresses her id to conform to societal norms. The suppression of Amina's id results from the events and affiliations that move into her consciousness. Thus, this study gives an insight into the psyche of the homosexual characters, which is in tune with the events that unfold in the novel.

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